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Brief Communication article

How attractive is the participation in a Living Lab study? Experimental evidence and recommendations

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Declarations

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Ethics and Open Science practices statement

Studies reported in this article were approved by the local Ethics committee at the University of Graz.

All materials, anonymized data, and codes are available from the Open Science Framework:

https://osf.io/8mr45/?view_only=f370c90bb22943edb2fd926169b359cb

All studies were preregistered before data analysis:

Study 1a: https://osf.io/35k7m/?view_only=59142ee33f924778920f603d600ab685,

Study 1b: https://osf.io/uyvh2/?view_only=f740d7254d454175ba42463295db2abc,

Study 2: https://osf.io/4ma3z/?view_only=945fee4450f44525a2dfde93e83efa6e

Author contribution

HB partly conceptualized and set up the studies, analyzed the data, managed the research data, and wrote the first draft of this article (40%); KM and KR partly conceptualized the studies, were in contact with other Living Lab projects, and gave feedback on the article (15% each); CA supported the technical setup of the studies (10%); MW partly conceptualized the study and commented on the article (5%); KC gave important feedback at all stages of this research, decided on the specific designs of the studies, and rewrote sections of the article draft (15%).

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Abstract

Living Labs – urban sites including households and workplaces to study the real-time usage of technological innovations and devices – have become increasingly popular among environmental scientists to gain insights into energy consumption in peoples' everyday life. However, recruiting a viable number of participants for such studies can pose a challenge to researchers: factors like month-long study durations, proficiency to handle smart technology, or frequent exchange with researchers and other users do not necessarily make a participation attractive for everyone. To identify relevant factors for participation, we conducted three large preregistered surveys (total N = 1,479) in Austria: two conjoint studies and one experimental study. We found that advertising a shorter Living Lab duration (less than a month), participation from home, and – crucially – financial incentives should be considered in promotion strategies and thorough study planning. However, we discuss that there might be a risk of selection bias for technic-savvy and future-oriented people.

Keywords: Living Lab, conjoint study, participation, energy consumption, incentives

1. Introduction

Originating from industry to test innovative technology [1, 2], Living Lab studies have become an increasingly popular domain in research, as they offer the unique opportunity to monitor participants' behavior in real-life settings. Such information is especially important, if one studies global challenges like the climate crises, which is a consequence of human behavior. To better understand when and why people do or do not act in a sustainable manner, behavioral scientists and psychologist set up Living Labs (LLs) – urban sites to study the usage of technological innovations and devices in real time [3] – with regard to diverse areas like mobility behavior, consumption, or household energy usage [4]. Because households and offices are two settings where people spend most of their daily time, they provide manifold opportunities to engage in sustainable behavior, such as energy saving, either for the sake of saving money or to reduce one's ecological footprint.

In LLs, these behaviors can be monitored by scientists in several informative ways. For instance, smart technologies can be tapped, such as digital electric meters to collect information on time courses of energy consumption, or smart plugs that monitor the energy consumption of individual devices. This way, suggestions can be generated, when and how often such devices should be used (e.g., to avoid daily peak times of high energy demand on the grid). Additional information can be gathered via questionnaires (e.g., on smartphones or tablets) on individual consumption patterns or on the user friendliness of certain devices. Based on this feedback, researchers can generate suggestions on how to design new and improve existing devices for future use. Moreover, if the investigated LLs are large enough, researchers can compare the performance of participating households, integrate and test gamification elements (e.g., leader boards on which household is most effective in saving energy), and organize co-creation workshop to assess and facilitate user experiences [5]. As one can see from this non-exhaustive list, there are diverse options to setup LLs to satisfy the needs of the researchers. However, so far these options have not been examined from the perspective of the participants.

It is unclear, which aspects of LLs would make a participation generally attractive to people in the first place. After all, participants have to provide information to researchers for several weeks or months. And being open about one's household behavior requires trust by the participants towards the researchers, whereas the researchers need to treat sensitive data with particular care and in accordance with national or supranational policy regulations (e.g., the General Data Protection Regulation of the European Union). In general, taking part in a LL study requires effort by the participants and if the thresholds (e.g., technical proficiency) are too high, and individual gains are too low, participants might not even consider to participate.

In three representative studies – two exploratory conjoint studies, and one confirmatory experimental main study – we aimed to test which aspects might make the participation in LLs attractive. From the exploratory conjoint studies, we deduced aspects that we then tested in the main experimental study along with additional moderating variables. Based on the study results,

we will provide suggestions to researchers, what to consider when they aim at conducting a LL study in the future.

2. Summary of Study 1a and 1b: Exploratory Conjoint Studies

Conjoint studies are characterized by the possibility to test several dimensions and aspects by which an object under investigation could differ and which could influence the preference of participants. In our case, the research object is the composition of LLs. We generated relevant dimensions based on our previous projects in the domain of green energy and user participation [6], previous considerations of how to define LLs in the literature [5, 7], digital law perspectives [8], and, importantly, consultations with other LL organizers (see OSF; https://osf.io/9t6jm/?view_only=f370c90bb22943edb2fd926169b359cb). All dimensions and their aspects that we deemed important are depicted in Fig. 1.

We set up two exploratory online questionnaires¹ in *LimeSurvey* [9] and *Pavlovia* [10], which we run via the Talk Online Panel (<https://talkonlinepanel.com/at/impressum>). In these questionnaires we introduced participants to the concept of LLs and the dimensions on which the setup could vary in a short video. Afterwards, we presented them successively with eight (Study 1a) or five (Study 1b) times two LL profiles to compare side by side. The LL profiles consisted of randomly drawn aspects for eight dimensions each. Participants indicated their preference for both presented profiles on seven-point rating scales (from 1 = “not preferred” to 7 = “very much preferred”) and also had to choose their preferred LL per page (i.e., the left or the right profile; see Fig. S1 on the OSF). Afterwards, they indicated their agreement with questions concerning their future orientation and present orientation (three items each, see [11]), as well as their technical affinity (four items, see [12]), all measured on six-point rating scales. We drew representative samples from the Austrian population (see Table 1 for descriptive information on Study 1a and 1b). Further information on the scales, methods, and power analysis [13, 14] can be found on the OSF.

Following state-of-the-art approaches in the literature [15, 16] and using the R packages *cjoint* [17], *lme4* [18], and *jmv* [19], we analyzed $k = 3696$ profiles in Study 1a and $k = 2980$ profiles in Study 1b and distilled the most preferred aspects via average marginal component effects (AMCEs). Results showed high preference ratings for financial *incentives* (medium and large incentives, 2 and 3, compared to no incentives, 1, AMCEs > 0.15 , $p < .001$). However, most other dimensions did not show large differences in preferences. Very small effects (AMCEs ~ 0.05) were observed for no *exchange* with others (3), which made LLs more attractive than direct or online exchange (1 and 2), shorter study *durations* of one month maximum (1 compare to 2 and 3), and participation from home (*location*, 1) instead of from a modern apartment (2). Effects of the remaining dimensions were too close to zero to be of relevance.

¹ Preregistrations: Study 1a: https://osf.io/35k7m/?view_only=59142ee33f924778920f603d600ab685; Study 1b: https://osf.io/uyvh2/?view_only=f740d7254d454175ba42463295db2abc

Fig. 1.

	1	2	3	evidence
Data processing	Data processing in anonymized form	Data processing in personalized form		X X
Data transfer	Rare data transfer for few appliances	Daily data transfer for several appliances	Continuous data transfer for the majority of appliances	X X
User exchange	Person-to-person exchange with other users	Virtual exchange with other users	No exchange with other users	✓ X
Focus	Focus on technical aspects	Focus on benefits for the environment / the society		X*
Learning	Unstructured learning through individual usage	Expert-supported learning through guided usage		X X
Duration	Duration of up to one month	Duration of up to six months	Duration of more than six months	✓ ✓
Incentives	No additional financial incentives	A bonus of 50 Euro	50 Euro bonus plus 10 Euro per hour	✓*
Questionnaires	Automatic data collection and no questionnaires	Weekly questionnaires (30 min) on user experiences	daily questionnaires (5 min) on user experiences	X X
Location	Participation from home	Participation in a modern, digitalized apartment		X ✓

Dimensions, aspects and summary results of the conjoint analysis. Note: dimensions are in rows and aspects per dimension are in columns; column for evidence signifies, whether evidence for at least a small effect (point estimate AMCE $\geq .05$ and $p < .05$) was found in Study 1a (checkmark left), 1b (checkmark right), in both, or in neither; * signifies that “incentives” was only used in Study 1a and “focus” was only used in Study 1b; details, see OSF

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for all three studies.

Variable	Study 1a		Study 1b		Study 2	
	M (SD)	% (n)	M (SD)	% (n)	M (SD)	% (n)
age	43.14 (14.46)		43.16 (14.41)		43.35 (14.16)	
income above 2.5k € net		46.6 (216)		53.4 (262)		53.8 (282)
high school or higher education		33.6 (153)		37.0 (182)		32.5 (170)
women*		48.5 (225)		48.2 (237)		51.5 (270)
cfc ($\alpha \geq .75$)	4.18 (1.03)		4.30 (0.94)		4.36 (0.99)	
cic ($\alpha \geq .77$)	3.05 (1.12)		3.02 (1.15)		2.62 (1.05)	
ati ($\alpha \geq .75$)	3.74 (1.06)		3.70 (1.14)		3.79 (1.51)	
N	464		491		524	

* Note: Study 1a, 1b, and 2, had $n = 2$, $n = 1$, and $n = 2$ gender diverse people, respectively; cfc = consideration of future consequences (future orientation), cic = consideration of immediate consequences (present orientation), ati = affinity for technology interaction (technical affinity)

3. Study 2: Confirmatory Experimental Study

In Study 2, we tested the consistency of the surprising finding of Study 1a that promoting exchange with other users would lead to *lower* attractiveness of LLs. To maximize the exchange effect in this experimental setting, we combined the variables *exchange* (with other users) with guided *learning* (through researchers), thereby emphasizing that participants could either explore the LL individually or in interaction with other users and researchers. Moreover, instead of introducing LLs in videos, we modified the *focus* condition from Study 1b by using digital flyers that were used to theoretically advertise the participation in LLs.²

Although neither *exchange* nor *focus* showed effects in Study 1b, we deemed these aspects relevant with regard to the overarching research question of factors for LL attractiveness, which would be crucial for promotion strategies.

3.1. Materials and Methods

For the variable *focus*, we created three flyers: the first advertised technical aspects of the Living Lab (tech), the second advertised sustainable energy usage in the Living Lab (green), the third advertised social participation in fair energy systems (social). Using *LimeSurvey* [9], we presented one of the flyers to participants as between-participants condition. *Exchange* with other users and researchers was then varied as a within-participants condition: The order of two (focus-wise similar) flyers was randomized and either contained information on interactions with other participants and researcher or on individual exploration only. We again asked for the attractiveness of the LL (dv1), whether participants would consider to participate (choice, dv2), and the overall attractiveness of the flyer as a control variable (all measured on seven-point scales, 1 = “not at all” to 7 = “very much”). In between both flyers, we again asked participants about their future and present orientation, as well as their technical affinity.

3.2. Results

With data from $N = 524$ participants, we conducted the 2 (within, *exchange*: none, much) \times 3 (between, *focus*: tech [$n = 195$], green [$n = 155$], social [$n = 174$]) mixed ANOVA with *attractiveness* of the Living Lab and whether they would consider participating (*choice*) as dependent variables. Results are depicted in Fig. 2 and show that neither factor made a difference: Independent of flyer design or – with respect to the hypothesis – emphasis on the exchange with others, participants rated the attractiveness with $M = 4.96$ ($SD = 1.29$) and choice with $M = 4.46$ ($SD = 1.68$).

We also measured participants technical affinity, their future orientation, and their orientation towards the present, which we added independently to the models. The former two, affinity (dv1: $F(2, 515) = 12.04$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .05$; dv2: $F(2, 515) = 22.68$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .08$) and future orientation (dv1: $F(2, 515) = 33.57$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .12$; dv2: $F(2, 515) = 19.70$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .07$) showed main effects across both dependent variables, with people high in affinity and future

² Preregistration Study 2: https://osf.io/4ma3z/?view_only=945fee4450f44525a2dfde93e83efa6e

orientation perceiving the LLs as more attractive than people low in affinity and low in future orientation – although these mean differences were mostly 0.5 scale points. Detailed results can be found in the supplemental document, Table S5-S16.

Fig. 2

focus $F(2, 521) = 1.36, p = .259, \eta_p^2 = .005$
exchange $F(1, 521) = 2.15, p = .143, \eta_p^2 = .004$
focus x exchange $F(2, 521) = 0.35, p = .706, \eta_p^2 = .001$

$F(2, 521) = 0.17, p = .842, \eta_p^2 = .001$
 $F(1, 521) < 0.00, p = .988, \eta_p^2 < .001$
 $F(2, 521) = 1.42, p = .242, \eta_p^2 = .005$

Results of the confirmatory analysis. Note: estimates represent means with 95% CIs; scatter represents participants in groups.

4. Discussion

As LLs have become increasingly attractive for researchers to receive information about people's energy consumption in real-life settings, we set out to test, which factors might make the participation in such a study attractive. After all, insights gained in LL studies may hold the promise to contribute to sustainable and pro-environmental behavior.

However, the results of our three studies are sobering: two exploratory conjoint studies showed that minimum interaction with other participants, short duration of the LL (less than one month), and participation from home (rather than in a newly built apartment) may be topics that could boost attractiveness to participate a little bit and financial incentives may do so a lot. However, these results – with the exception of the financial dimensions – are likely unstable in real advertisements of LLs, as we showed in Study 2, where we could not replicate the somewhat surprising effect that little exchange with other users is attractive. Moreover, although the flyers were meant to increase the effect of the *focus* dimension, it did not make a difference, if technical, green, or social aspects were emphasized as a motivation to participate in a LL study. Instead, we found some evidence that people with a high future orientation in their decision making and with a high affinity towards technology preferred a participation more than people scoring low on these scales.

A crucial limitation of our studies is that they simulated one-shot and low-cost recruitment strategies: participants decided on the attractiveness of LLs based on videos or flyer information and knew that they would not actually be recruited for such a study. Hence, their overall slightly positive attractiveness ratings may just represent a response bias that reflect a neutral position. Additionally, the effects of the psychological predictors future orientation and technology affinity might point to a larger problem: potentially, the recruitment for LLs studies could result in a selection bias independent of advertisement strategies. If mainly these two groups of people feel addressed, inferences drawn from LL studies might also be limited to these groups.

Suggestions and Future Directions

LL studies are a promising avenue to get unique insights into household energy consumption. Using LLs, suggestions can be made on how to improve new and smart technology to support people in adopting a more energy-efficient and sustainable behavior. However, our current studies showed that recruitment for such a study will require effort, especially, if it is supposed to be representative for the population.

Researchers who aim at conducting a LL study are advised to devote both a lot of time and financial resources during their study planning for recruitment. We suggest that researchers plan ahead of their projects with local authorities and private organizations, how the advertisement for such a study can be organized. Advertisements may include newspaper and social media adds and person-to-person advertisement at public places (outside the university campus). Personal contact and exchange of experience with other researchers, who conducted LL studies before, may also help to identify useful strategies.

As financial compensation turned out the most prominent factor, we also suggest to researchers to provide financial incentives, which might vary according to socio-demographic groups (e.g., higher bonuses for lower-income groups) and with regard to study duration (e.g., mile-stone incentives to counteract a dropout and attrition rate). Not all of these measures will be actionable in all contexts, but careful planning might increase the participation rate.

Conclusion

In sum, we studied the attractiveness of LLs utilizing three large samples. We found very limited evidence for few factors that could be used in advertising for LL studies, including shorter study duration and participation from home. Prominently, financial incentives stood out as the largest factor. We suggest that researchers, who want to conduct a LL study should actively plan for incentives and advertising strategies that go beyond low-cost recruitment strategies.

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